

THE ROLE OF PUBLIC POLICY IN WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT: INCREASING KNOWLEDGE, EMPLOYMENT, AND ATTITUDES

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the measures aimed at improving the socio-economic status of women, expanding their knowledge, employment and outlook within the framework of the state policy in Uzbekistan. In the field of education, the foundation is laid for the academic and professional development of women through initiatives that include incentives, scholarships, and special training programs. In the field of employment and entrepreneurship support, economic programs for women such as "Women's Book", loans and grants help to ensure financial independence of women. Also, by expanding political participation, women have the opportunity to participate more actively in political processes, which serves to increase their influence in society. These initiatives are aimed at strengthening the position of women in society and improving their overall quality of life. In addition, there are special programs aimed at women in the health sector as well. Maternal and child protection and reproductive health initiatives are aimed at ensuring women's health and improving their quality of life. Strengthening the role of women in society and family, increasing their political and social activity is one of the main directions of state policy. At the same time, through international cooperation and exchange programs, the worldview of women is being expanded, which encourages their active participation in global issues. These political and social initiatives are important steps aimed at achieving gender equality in Uzbekistan and increasing the status of women in society.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, women's empowerment is not only a matter of social justice, but also a crucial component of national development. State policy plays an important role in raising the status of women, expanding their educational opportunities, ensuring their employment and expanding their worldview. This article explores how government strategies can increase women's role in society, empower them through education, secure employment and expand their prospects. Education is the foundation of women's empowerment. Public policies that prioritize women's education lead to higher literacy rates, which open up opportunities for further education and employment. Initiatives such as scholarships for girls, promotion work aimed at rural areas, and the establishment of women's universities are important. In recent years, great changes have been made in Uzbekistan to improve the social and economic status of women. The government of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has launched a number of political and economic initiatives to support women and strengthen their position in society. These initiatives cover areas as diverse as education, employment, health and political participation. In order to expand the right of women to education, the government of Uzbekistan pays special attention to the expansion and improvement of the quality of the preschool education system. In addition, scholarships and special training programs have been introduced to encourage the

study of women in higher education institutions. Through these initiatives, women can continue their professional and personal development. President Mirziyoyev's government attaches great importance to providing employment to women and supporting their entrepreneurial activities. In this regard, measures are being taken to help women facing economic difficulties through initiatives such as "Women's Notebook". Also, loans and grants are provided to support women's entrepreneurship, which allows them to start and develop their own businesses. There are also special programs aimed at women in the health sector. In particular, programs on motherhood and childhood protection, reproductive health care have been strengthened. These programs are aimed at ensuring women's health and improving their quality of life. Many opportunities are being created for women to participate more actively in political processes in Uzbekistan. For example, political training courses are being organized for women and measures are being taken to encourage them to participate in public administration. In addition, the number of women's representation in the Oliy Majlis is increasing, which ensures their full participation in the legislative process.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The purpose of the study is to study the role of state policy in improving the education, employment and outlook of women in Uzbekistan. To achieve this goal, the methodology of the research includes a number of scientific methods, which evaluate the effectiveness of state programs aimed at improving the socio-economic status of women. A number of decisions and orders with the initiative of Sh.M. Mirziyoyev are giving their results in practice. An example of this is the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-87 dated 07.03.2022 "ON MEASURES TO FURTHER ACCELERATE WORKS ON SYSTEMATIC SUPPORT OF THE FAMILY AND WIVES." This decree protects the rights and legal interests of women in Uzbekistan, increases their economic, social and political activity, protects their health, provides vocational training and employment, wide involvement in entrepreneurship, and women in need. was adopted in order to systematically continue the ongoing reforms to ensure social support and gender equality. The decree sets out a number of important initiatives, including:

The National program for increasing the activity of women in economic, political and social life in 2022-2026 and the comprehensive plan of measures aimed at its implementation have been approved.

It is determined that women will be paid pregnancy and childbirth benefits, and the amount of these benefits will be covered from the state budget.

In order to create favorable conditions for women's education, allocating educational loans for women studying in higher education institutions, covering the contract fees of women studying at the master's level from the state budget. held in

It is envisaged that additional grants will be allocated to women studying in foreign higher education institutions through the "Hope of the Country" fund.

It is indicated that the educational contracts of socially needy women and orphan girls will be covered from the local budget funds.

Also, the decree defines a number of other measures, such as supporting the scientific and innovative activities of women, attracting women to entrepreneurship, increasing their scientific potential, and implementing the results of scientific research. This decree is an

important step aimed at ensuring gender equality in Uzbekistan and strengthening the position of women in society.

In addition, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 145 dated 31.03.2022 "ON MEASURES FOR FURTHER IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF STUDYING AND SOLUTION OF WOMEN'S PROBLEMS" i.e., "Women's Notebook" the system provides legal, psychological, medical and financial assistance to women in difficult socio-economic conditions. The decision includes the following main points:

1. Special funds will be established to help women with "Women's Notebook". These funds are financed by various levels of hokims and managed by the Board of Trustees.
2. Specific measures will be developed and financed to solve the socio-economic problems of women included in the "Women's Register". Among them, providing employment, engaging in entrepreneurship, providing material support, and solving housing issues take an important place.
3. The State Committee for Family and Women and other responsible ministries and agencies actively participate in the management of this system and help to increase their social activity. Also, the document envisages a number of other activities, such as involving some women in entrepreneurship, providing them with social protection, and providing various medical care. Through this decision, the government seeks to improve the living standards of women and strengthen their position in society.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The measures taken to expand the socio-economic opportunities of women through the state policy and their impact are studied. In this analysis, based on the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers, the work carried out on the systematic solution of women's problems and their social support is highlighted.

In the state policy, special attention is paid to improving the knowledge and skills of women. Initiatives have been taken to attract unemployed women to vocational training and send them to retraining courses through the "Women's Directory" system. These courses are organized not only for traditional professions, but also based on modern requirements, which serve to increase the competitiveness of women in the market.

A number of approaches have also been used in the field of employment of women. In particular, it is planned to employ women included in the list of "Women's Register" in local jobs, newly created positions in the public and private sector. In addition, we help women to become entrepreneurs and increase their economic independence by providing loans and grants to start their own businesses.

The expansion of women's outlook is closely related to changes in society. Therefore, various seminars and meetings held within the framework of "Women's Notebook" serve to expand their worldview by engaging women in dialogue on important issues in society, instilling in them new ideas. Through these, women better understand their rights and try to apply them in practice.

Based on the policies implemented by the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the role and opportunities of women in society are significantly increased. However, it is important to continue systematic monitoring and analysis, as well as to support women's aspirations for self-development, in order to further increase the effectiveness of state policy. In this regard, it is

necessary to strengthen cooperation between the state, public organizations and local authorities.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-87 of March 7, 2022 "On measures to further accelerate work on systematic support for families and women" and Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2022 Resolution No. 145 of March 31 "On measures to further improve the system of studying and solving women's problems" is an important document aimed at strengthening gender equality and increasing the social and economic activity of women in the country. The work carried out on the basis of these documents demonstrates the effectiveness of state policy and greatly contributes to the expansion of women's education, employment and outlook.

Practical measures: within the framework of the "Family and Women's Support" program, to organize special courses on providing women with work and improving their professional skills. To further expand the system of microloans and grants in order to attract women to entrepreneurship. Education and training: Development and implementation of educational programs for women, especially for women living in rural areas. Organization of special programs aimed at developing women's technology and digital skills. Formation of public opinion: activation of media campaigns aimed at promoting the ideas of gender equality and strengthening the position of women in society. Strengthen outreach to involve women in political and social activities. The implementation of these proposals will not only expand the economic and social opportunities of women, but also serve to strengthen the socio-economic stability of the country as a whole.

Адабиётлар руйхати:

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2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 07.03.2022 yildagi PF-87-son "Oila va xotin-qizlarni tizimli qo'llab-quvvatlashga doir ishlarni yanada jadallashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida" farmoni.
3. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining qarori, 08.11.2022 yildagi 650-son "Mahallalarda xotin-qizlarning bandligini ta'minlash va salomatligini mustahkamlash markazlari faoliyatini tashkil etish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida".
4. "Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi va ayollar bandligi" Bibisara Abibullayevna Erejepova
5. "Jamiyatda ayollarning ijtimoiy roli" Berdiyeva Shoiraxonovna
6. "Ayollarning ijtimoiy-siyosiy hayotdagi roli" Xaydarova Anora.
7. "Yangi o'zbekiston jamiyatida ayollarning o'ri" Ziyodaxon To'g'onboyeva